

Simulation of the Performance of Iron Pyrite Thin Film Solar Cell by SCAPS 1-D

(Simulasi Tahap Prestasi Sel Suria Jenis Filem Nipis Ferum Disulfida Berdasarkan SCAPS 1-D)

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ABSTRACT

Iron pyrite (FeS₂) is the material that have a higher absorption coefficient and potential to be alternative material to replace CIGS because of its abundance element and non-toxicity than CIGS which is have rare element such as indium and gallium. This study was conducted to study the performance of FeS₂ thin film solar cell as a p type semiconductor in solar cell by using simulation from SCAPS 1-D software. Maximum conversion efficiency of FeS₂ solar cells demonstrated to date, however, is below 3%, which is significantly below the theoretical efficiency limit of 25%. This poor conversion efficiency is mainly the result of the poor photovoltage, which has never exceeded 0.2 V with a device having appreciable photocurrent. In this study, electrical properties and physical properties of FeS₂ will be analysis for increasing the performance efficiency of FeS₂ inside of completed model structure of solar cell. Electrical properties and physical of FeS₂ that will be manipulate are the thickness, carrier density, band gap and electron mobility. Next, the numerical modelling will be done for increasing the performance of FeS₂ to optimum power. The performance of FeS₂ are determined by their efficiency, fill factor, short circuit current density, and pen circuit voltage. The result of the study had shown the performance of FeS₂ is affected by every single electrical characteristic of FeS₂ that have been manipulated. Finally, the performance FeS₂ had shown improvement by using the simulation technique and suggestions of a few research directions are also presented.

Keywords: Solar Cell, Conversion Efficiency, Performance

ABSTRAK

Ferum disulfida (FeS₂) merupakan bahan yang mempunyai pekali penyerapan yang tinggi dan berpotensi sebagai bahan alternatif untuk menggantikan CIGS kerana unsurnya mudah didapati dan tanpa toksin berbanding CIGS yang mempunyai unsur yang sukar ditemui seperti indium dan galium. Kajian ini dilakukan untuk mengkaji prestasi sel suria jenis filem nipis FeS₂ sebagai bahan semikonduktor jenis p dalam sel suria dengan kaedah simulasi menggunakan perisian SCAPS 1-D. Penukaran kecekapan maksima FeS₂ telah diperolehi, walaubagaimanapun, rendah daripada 3% dan menunjukkan perbezaan yang ketara dengan penukaran kecekapan teori iaitu 25%. Tahap penukaran yang kecekapan yang rendah telah menyebabkan hasil fotovoltan yang rendah, tidak mencecah 0.2 V dengan arusfoton yang sederhana terhadap peranti tersebut. Dalam kajian ini, sifat elektrik dan fizikal FeS₂ akan dianalisis bagi meningkatkan tahap prestasi kecekapan FeS₂ dalam satu model struktur sel suria yang lengkap. Sifat elektrik dan fizikal FeS₂ yang akan dimanipulasi adalah ketebalan, ketumpatan penerima, jurang jalur dan kelincahan elektron. Seterusnya, kaedah pemodelan berangka dibuat untuk mendapatkan nilai kecekapan yang optimum terhadap FeS₂. Prestasi FeS₂ akan ditentukan oleh kecekapan, faktor isi, jumlah arus litar pintas dan voltan litar buka sel suria tersebut. Hasil kajian telah mendapati setiap sifat elektrik yang dimanipulasi memberi kesan terhadap prestasi FeS₂. Kesimpulannya, prestasi FeS₂ telah menunjukkan peningkatan dari segi kaedah simulasi dan sedikit cadangan untuk kajian akan datang telah dinyatakan.

Kata Kunci: Sel Suria, Penukaran Kecekapan, Prestasi

INTRODUCTION

The greenhouse effect causes global warming, which is defined as an increase in average

global temperatures. Certain gases in the atmosphere operate like greenhouse glass, allowing sunlight to warm the earth's surface while storing the heat as it radiates back into space. The Earth becomes hotter as greenhouse gases pile up in the atmosphere. One

of the major factors of greenhouse effect was from the coal-fired power plant. Coal-fired power plants are a type of power plant that generates electricity by using combustion coal. The gases from coal-fired plant have affected the atmosphere layer become thinner and causes global warming. The effect can be reduced by replacing a coal-fired power plants with renewable power plant such as solar farm which is using solar energy to electrical energy.

Solar energy, often known as solar power, is the conversion of solar energy into electricity, which can be done directly using photovoltaics (PV), indirectly using concentrated solar energy, or a mix of both. Solar tracking systems and lenses or mirrors are used in concentrated solar energy systems to focus huge amounts of sunlight into little rays. Photo-voltage cells use photo-voltage effects to convert light into electrical current. Panels, inverters, racks, and solar battery storage units are the four basic components of a solar energy system (if required). Solar panels are the most visible component of solar energy systems, and numerous solar cells comprised of wafer-based crystalline silicon cells or thin film cells are used in solar panels. Second-generation solar cells are formed by spreading one or more thin layers, or a thin film (TF), of photovoltaic material on a substrate such as glass, plastic, or metal. In this study, pyrite thin film solar has been used to be simulate.

Pyrite (FeS_2) has long been recognized as a material with high potential as a solar absorber for photovoltaic devices (Rahman et al. 2020). This is due to pyrite's exceptional absorption coefficient ($>10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ above 1.2–1.4 eV rendering a less than 100 nm thick-film capable of absorbing over 90% of the sun's light), good mobility ($>300 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in single crystal form), and a suitable minority carrier diffusion length (100–1000 nm). However, its low open-circuit voltage ($V_{\text{OC}} < 0.2 \text{ eV}$) resulted from its narrow band gap of $E_g = 0.95 \text{ eV}$ leads to its low photoelectric conversion efficiency of 3% (Uchiyama et al. 2016), (Bhandari et al. 2017). Recently, various causes have been proposed to explain its low V_{OC} , including bulk defects, low intensity states at the bottom of the conduction band, intrinsic surface states and the presence of competing phases.

In this study, we develop one simple model structure for FeS_2 and investigated the performance of FeS_2 and examined conversion efficiency by using device simulation SCAPS 1-D. Furthermore, we modeled a device structure of n-semiconductor which can achieve high efficiency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding of Photovoltage Loss in Iron Pyrite Solar Cells

FeS_2 offers possibilities of the lowest priced electricity production among the known solar cell

materials. However, FeS_2 solar cells never have exceeded a PCE greater than 2.8% (Luo et al. 2015; Zhang et al. 2015). The fundamental difficulties behind this poor conversion efficiency have been documented as surface conduction phenomena and unwanted doping, which then lead to phenomena including surface inversion, ionization of deep donor states, and photocarrier recombination for photovoltage loss.

Increase Band Gap FeS_2 by Doping

Doping is a typical method for mediating the band gap of semiconductors by substituting isovalent elements for cations or anions. To boost the VOC of pyrite, doping with larger band gap material is used. Zn has been mentioned as a potential focus for future research. ZnS_2 is thought to have a band gap of 2.5 eV. Of all other known pyrite type candidates, including CoS_2 , MnS_2 , CuS_2 , NiS_2 , RuS_2 , and OsS_2 , however, CoS_2 is an itinerant electron ferromagnet below $T_c = 120 \text{ K}$, MnS_2 , CuS_2 are metallic materials, NiS_2 is not suitable to alloying with pyrite because its lower band gap. The remaining candidates are ZnS_2 , RuS_2 ($E_g^{\text{expt}} = 1.3 \text{ eV}$) and OsS_2 ($E_g^{\text{expt}} = 2.0 \text{ eV}$). In cation doping, the bowing effect will decrease the band gap when alloying with Zn, while Ru and Os alloying slightly increase the band gap. It is a very successful approach to increase the band gap by doping oxygen atoms in anion doping. Density functional theory shows that doping oxygen atoms can raise the band gap of FeS_2 by roughly 0.2–0.3 eV without creating gap states (DFT) (Liu & Zhang 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Overview

There are several steps that need to be followed to complete this study. In the first stage, the data parameter of each layer collected from the various articles and develop a simple solar cell model structure for FeS_2 . In the second stage, the simulation was performed to determined the FeS_2 performance by inspect the efficiency, open circuit voltage, fill factor, and short circuit current density. Lastly, we modeled a device structure of n-semiconductor which can achieve high efficiency.

DATA COLLECTING AND MODEL STRUCTURE

Table 1 shows the collected data parameter for each layer from the various articles. The data is used for the simulation for determined the performance of FeS_2 . Source from (Xiao et al.

2014),(Altermatt et al. 2002),(Yu et al. 2015) and (Hossain et al. 2018).

	Al:ZnO	n-CdS	p-FeS ₂
Thickness (µm)	200	0.05	0.9
Band gap (eV)	3.3	2.4	0.8
Electron affinity (eV)	4.6	4.2	4.5
Dielectric permittivity (relative)	9	10	13.6
CB effective density of states (cm ⁻³)	2.2x10 ¹⁸	2.2x10 ¹⁸	3x10 ¹⁸
VB effective density of states (cm ⁻³)	1.8x10 ¹⁹	1.8x10 ¹⁹	8.5x10 ¹⁹
Electron thermal velocity (cm/s)	1x10 ⁷	1x10 ⁷	1x10 ⁷
Hole thermal velocity (cm/s)	1x10 ⁷	1x10 ⁷	1x10 ⁷
Hole thermal velocity (cm ² /Vs)	1x10 ²	1x10 ²	1x10 ²
Hole mobility (cm ² /Vs)	25	25	2x10 ⁻²

TABLE 1 Layer for each parameter.

The simple model structure of solar cell created by the ideas from the articles. Al: ZnO as metal, CdS as n-type semiconductor and FeS₂ as p-type semiconductor as refer of FIGURE 1. The simulation will be conduct by the followed model structure.

FIGURE 1 Model Structure

SIMULATION AND NUMERICAL MODELING

FIGURE 2 Flow chart simulation of SCAPS 1-D

SCAPS is a window application program, developed at the University of Gent with lab windows/CVI of the national instrument. The program organized in a number of panels in which the user can set the parameters or in which the results are calculated. SCAPS analyses the physics of the model and it explains the recombination profiles, electric field distribution, carrier transport mechanism and individual current densities (Mandadapu 2017). The simulation of FeS₂ followed as mentioned by flow chart in FIGURE 2. To find out the best performance of solar cell, the optimum parameter of FeS₂ must be used and find out by using the simulation proses. The simulation set working condition 300 °K as the temperature and 1x10⁶ Hz frequency and 1000 Wm⁻² power of solar energy from the sun. The simulation will determined the performance FeS₂ by manipulate the variable of thickness, acceptor density, band gap and acceptor density of FeS₂ by using the most optimum value. Lastly, numerical modelling for n-type semiconductor to achieve a high efficiency by manipulate it donor density.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimum Parameter

The simulation will find out optimum value parameter by manipulated the acceptor density and the thickness of FeS₂. It simulated from 100 μm until 1000 μm with the difference 100 μm for each simulation while the acceptor density we are using 1x10¹³ cm⁻³ until 1x10¹⁸ cm⁻³ with difference 1x10⁵ cm⁻³ for each simulation.

	Acceptor Density NA (cm⁻³)	Thickness (μm)
η (%)	1x10 ¹⁶	900
FF (%)	1x10 ¹⁶	900
J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	1x10 ¹⁶	200
V _{oc} (V)	1x10 ¹⁶	400

TABLE 2 Optimum parameter for acceptor density and the thickness.

Table 2 show the optimum value of acceptor density and thickness for performance of FeS₂. From the simulation 900 μm is the optimum value should use to get the good value of the performance. When the thickness increases the efficiency and fill factor of FeS₂ likely to get a higher value. For the acceptor density, 1x10¹⁶ cm⁻³ show the best result of performance of the solar cell. The 900 μm of thickness and 1x10¹⁶ cm⁻³ of acceptor density will be remain and use for the next simulation.

Next, the optimum parameter from previous simulation will be remain for find out the next optimum value for FeS₂. The simulation proses into next step by manipulated the value of parameter of band gap and electron mobility. To find the optimum value, the simulation started by using a band gap from 0.8 eV until 1.3 eV with difference 0.1 eV for each simulation and electron mobility from 1.5x10² cm²/Vs until 4.0x10² cm²/Vs with difference 0.5x10² cm²/Vs for each simulation.

	Electron Mobility (cm²/Vs)	Band Gap (eV)
η (%)	1.50x10 ²	1.3
FF (%)	1.50x10 ²	1.3
J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	4.0x10 ²	0.8
V _{oc} (V)	1.50x10 ²	1.3

TABLE 3 Optimum parameter for electron mobility and band gap of FeS₂.

Table 3 show the optimum value of the electron mobility and band gap for each factor. From the result, 1.50x10² cm²/Vs of electron was the optimum value for electron mobility since it promising the high value of efficiency, fill factor and open-circuit voltage except for short circuit current

density. The lower the electron mobility will result the good performance. As for the band gap, the higher the band, the good the performance. From the simulation 1.3 eV of band gap also promising the high value of efficiency, fill factor and open-circuit voltage except for short circuit current density same as electron mobility.

Numerical Modelling

To achieve the high efficiency in solar cell. The next step is produced a numerical modeling toward the n type semiconductor which is CdS. To boost the performance of solar cell FeS₂ to optimum. The donor density of CdS will be the parameter will be simulated. The value will be simulated from 1.0x10¹⁵ 1/cm³ until 1.0x10²⁰ 1/cm³ with differences 1.0x10¹ 1/cm³ for each simulation.

Donor density (1/cm³)	η (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm²)	V_{oc} (V)
1.0x10 ¹⁵	9.91	51.02	32.3804	0.6002
1.0x10 ¹⁶	10.54	55.93	32.3632	0.5821
1.0x10 ¹⁷	13.57	75.77	31.8283	0.5627
1.0x10 ¹⁸	12.04	76.31	27.9373	0.5646
1.0x10 ¹⁹	11.92	76.34	27.6370	0.5648
1.0x10 ²⁰	11.88	76.35	27.5444	0.5648

TABLE 4 Optimum parameter for donor density of CdS.

Table 4 show the result of simulation of changing the value of donor density. From the simulation the higher efficiency recorded is 13.57 % by using 1.0 x 10¹⁷ (1/cm³). The high value of donor density used, the high value of fill factor will produced but inverserly toward volatge open circuit. As the objective is to get the higher efficiency of FeS₂. The value 1.0 x 10¹⁷ (1/cm³) will consider as the suitable value use to increase the performance of FeS₂.

Performance of FeS₂

The simulation proses have develop the new optimum value parameter used to increasing the performance of thin film solar cell FeS₂. As result it show some improvement toward solar cell of FeS₂. The simulation has proven some parameter will give a huge effect toward performance FeS₂.

FIGURE 2. (a) Absorption spectra of ZnO, (b) ZnMn_{0.05}O and (c) ZnMn_{0.10}O.

Figure 2 show the spectrum graph for each electric characteristic of FeS₂. The final result recorded the efficiency was 13.57%, fill factor is 75.77%, 31.82838 mA/cm² for J_{SC} dan 0.5627 V for V_{OC}. The result from simulation have shown the improvement toward FeS₂. As mentioned before the higher efficiency of pyrite that have been required is 2.8% which is a little bit lower for the thin film solar cell with a good absorption coefficient. From the simulation the efficiency have improvent to 13.57 % but still it shown a huge difference towards the theoretical value which is up to 25 %. The high Voc produce from the simulation have causes the high of J_{SC} in FeS₂.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion from the journal that have been study the simulation toward FeS₂ have shown some improvement toward its performance. Each parameter that have been used is the logical value from the articles and some is from the modification of FeS₂ which defect FeS₂. The pyrite solar cell having the architecture Al:ZnO/FeS₂/CdS is designed and analyzed using Solar cell capacitance simulator. Absorber layer thickness, acceptor density, band gap and electron mobility influence on the performance of the solar cell are investigated and the numerical modelling have shown effect on the PV, characteristics are observed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Prof Madya Dr Badariah Bais and Dr Puvaneswaran A/L Chelvanathan from Solar Energy Research Institute

(SERI), Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia for their moral support, knowledge provided and also for their technical support.

REFERENCES

- Altermatt, P. P., Kiesewetter, T., Ellmer, K. & Tributsch, H. 2002. Specifying targets of future research in photovoltaic devices containing pyrite (FeS₂) by numerical modelling. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 71(2): 181–195. doi:10.1016/S0927-0248(01)00053-8
- Bhandari, K. P., Tan, X., Zereshki, P., Alfidhili, F. K., Phillips, A. B., Koirala, P., Heben, M. J., et al. 2017. Thin film iron pyrite deposited by hybrid sputtering/co-evaporation as a hole transport layer for sputtered CdS/CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 163(January): 277–284. doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2017.01.044
- Hossain, E. S., Chelvanathan, P., Shahahmadi, S. A., Sopian, K., Bais, B. & Amin, N. 2018. Performance assessment of Cu₂SnS₃ (CTS) based thin film solar cells by AMPS-1D. *Current Applied Physics* 18(1): 79–89. doi:10.1016/j.cap.2017.10.009
- Liu, T. L. & Zhang, J. M. 2020. Feasibility of band gap engineering of iron pyrite (FeS₂) by codoping Os, Ru or Zn together with O. *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 244(October 2019): 122742. doi:10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.122742
- Luo, L., Luan, W., Yuan, B., Zhang, C. & Jin, L. 2015. High Efficient and Stable Solid Solar Cell: Based on FeS₂ Nanocrystals and P3HT: PCBM. *Energy Procedia* 75: 2181–2186. doi:10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.368
- Mandadapu, U. 2017. Simulation and Analysis of Lead based Perovskite Solar Cell using SCAPS-1D. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology* 10(1): 1–8. doi:10.17485/ijst/2017/v11i10/110721
- Rahman, M., Boschloo, G., Hagfeldt, A. & Edvinsson, T. 2020. On the Mechanistic Understanding of Photovoltage Loss in Iron Pyrite Solar Cells. *Advanced Materials* 32(26). doi:10.1002/adma.201905653
- Uchiyama, S., Ishikawa, Y., Kawamura, Y. & Uraoka, Y. 2016. Numerical modeling of device structure for FeS₂ thin film solar cells. *Proceedings of AM-FPD 2016 - 23rd*

*International Workshop on Active-Matrix
Flatpanel Displays and Devices: TFT
Technologies and FPD Materials* 215–218.
doi:10.1109/AM-FPD.2016.7543671

- Xiao, P., Fan, X. L., Liu, L. M. & Lau, W. M.
2014. Band gap engineering of FeS₂ under
biaxial strain: A first principles study.
Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics 16(44):
24466–24472. doi:10.1039/c4cp03453h
- Yu, P., Qu, S., Jia, C., Liu, K. & Tan, F. 2015.
Modified synthesis of FeS₂ quantum dots for
hybrid bulk-heterojunction solar cells.
Materials Letters 157: 235–238.
doi:10.1016/j.matlet.2015.05.033
- Zhang, X., Scott, T., Socha, T., Nielsen, D.,
Manno, M., Johnson, M., Yan, Y., et al.
2015. Phase Stability and Stoichiometry in
Thin Film Iron Pyrite: Impact on Electronic
Transport Properties. *ACS Applied Materials
and Interfaces* 7(25): 14130–14139.
doi:10.1021/acsami.5b03422